

Stakeholders Perception on Influence of Insurgencies on Pupils' Enrollment and Achievement of Quality Primary Education in Selected Educational Zones in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract: Insurgencies has greatly affected several sectors of Nigerian economy such as Agriculture, health, commerce and most especially educational sector that is the foundation upon which other sectors is built. The level of pupils' enrolment and attainment of quality education in Katsina State over the years is significantly declining due to several factors like unqualified teachers recruitment, poor funding to education, poor welfare of teachers and most especially impact of insurgencies. The researchers therefore feel deeply worried to carry out this research work titled "Stakeholders' perception on influence of insurgencies on primary school pupils' enrolment and achievement of quality education in selected educational zone in Katsina state, Nigeria" aimed at addressing the causes and impact of insurgencies in Nigeria with emphasis in Katsina State. The study adopt survey research design. The target population is all the teachers and head teachers from Katsina and Dutsin-ma educational Zones respectively. The study used structured questionnaires for gathering data while descriptive and inferential statistics was used to analyze data collected and answer research questions. The study reveal that insurgency have affected primary school enrollment of children and attainment of quality education. It was recommended that acquiring entrepreneurship skills education after graduation will enable young graduate to be self-employed without waiting for white collar job or join bad wagon of terrorists after graduation, improved security measures Such as installation of surveillance cameras as well as posting of adequate personnel should be posted around school environment to avert insurgency attacks and adequate funding should be allocated to education sector as recommended by UNESCO at both national and state level to cater for teachers' training and welfare to enable them put in their best by giving the pupils desired quality education.

Key points: Insurgencies, Enrollment and Achievement

Introduction

Knowledge and wisdom liberate people out of the bondage of ignorance, illiteracy and poverty leading to growth and development. Conversely, ignorance, illiteracy, and poverty enslave people in the circle of continuous retrogress and under development, while corruption, injustice and dishonesty always put the society in the state of confusion, crises and doom. Education is the light

through which individual, community and the Nation can see the route to growth and development. Regrettably, education have been witnessing several challenges due to the failure of parents to live up to their responsibilities in giving the desired care and training to their children to become responsible and productive citizens rather than destructive citizens and also the failure of government to fulfil its constitutional roles to ensure that all children's of school age acquire compulsory free primary education as stipulated in article No. 3 of the 1989 and 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria which states that "Education is the birth right of Nigerian citizen" (Haruna 2023).

Parental and governmental roles are key to peaceful coexistence in Nigeria. This is because both the parents and the government are determinants of peace, growth and development in our society if the desired attention and care are given to their children and the citizens to become patriotic Citizens rather than creating unrest, war and violence as we are experiencing today. The insurgency situation in Nigeria is on the increase on daily basis in Nigeria and Katsina State in particular and this may affect children's enrollment and achievement of quality primary Education. Nigeria that is said to be the giant of Africa has been a relatively peaceful, multicultural, dynamic and progressive nation. The country is blessed with both human and natural resources, which paved ways for many opportunities for its citizens and foreigners to live in harmony from the colonial era. From the inception of Nigeria independence in October 1, 1960 up to the year 2000, the country started experiencing the strange, and global trend of terrorism, insurgency which led to the gruesome killings of innocent Nigerian citizens by an insurgent group called Boko Haram. Since 2009, they have been disrupting the educational system in Nigeria with huge negative impact on quality primary education. There is massive destruction of school activities in North Eastern Nigeria and currently in North Western Nigeria. Before the current insurgency, Nigeria had witnessed several forms of terrorism which is a systematic use of violence to destroy, kidnap and intimidate the innocent citizens in order to draw national attention to their demands with the Nigerian government (Olawuwo, Atiku, & Hussaini, 2023)

However, some of these past terrorist attacks are politically motivated, even though some may have other strong motives such as socio-economic and regional marginalization issues. They posited that, before the declaration of amnesty for Niger Delta youths by the Nigerian Government in 2008, the Niger Delta region had militant groups such as Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), Movement for the Survival of Ogoni People (MOSOP), Niger Delta People Volunteer Force (NDPVF). These militant groups launched agitation against crude oil spillage, poverty and marginalization of the Niger Delta people of the South-South region of Nigeria. The Oduduwa People's Congress (OPC) is the militating wing and frontier of the Yoruba people in the South Western Region of Nigeria demanding for their political right. Passionately, the region served as entry point of western education into Nigeria. They were educationally developed as most of the citizen past through formal education, which posed as a stumbling block that hindered the militia group from having a strong base in South Western Region of Nigeria. In the South Eastern Region of Nigeria, the Movement for the Actualizations of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB) and the Bakassi boys were also militia groups fighting for equal rights and security of Igbo federalism, autonomy and political relevance of the Igbo people in Nigeria. Fundamentally, it was used by dominant political group in the region to advance their courses and achieve recognition. In 1981, the "Maitatsine" Jihadist group leader Mohammed Marwa, who came from Northern Cameroon via Borno State in Nigeria. Mohammed Marwa proclaimed himself as a prophet of Islam, used violence to kill many citizens in Northern Nigeria to achieve his religious principles. He received negative response from the people, and could not actualize his dream as he was killed during gun battle with the Nigerian forces (Olawuwo, etal 2023). Currently the nation is witnessing high spate of insurgency such as kidnapping, banditry, cattle rustlers and Herdsmen attack especially in the North Western Nigerian States like Katsina, Kaduna, Kano, Kebbi, Sokoto, and Zamfara States.

Statement of the problem

One of the major challenges of stable educational system and policies and programs in Nigeria is insurgent attacks on school activities. The brutal insurgency has affected every strata of Nigerian economy especially, education sector. Educational activities in Nigeria are exposed to threats and attacks as a result of lack of intelligence gathering and failure on the part of government to adequately protect schools coupled with uncondusive teaching and learning environment Abiodun, Opatoki, Adeyemo, & Obi (2020). Over the years, Katsina State used to be one of the most peaceful part of the country, but in recent time, precisely, during the Buhari administration, between 2015 to 2023, Katsina State has started recording cases of insurgency of different types such as banditry, kidnapping, and cattle rustlers that led the closure of schools in many Local Government Areas (LGAs) of the State. This is affecting the attainment of quality primary education in the state. Children that are said to be the leaders of tomorrow have not received the desired attention in terms of quality education despite the efforts of the Federal and State Governments in providing basic education to its citizens. This is probably due to lack of maintenance of educational facilities, recruitment of unqualified teachers, corruption, inadequate funding, and insufficient teachers in most of the primary schools. Others include limited information about the security situation in the area, poor teachers' welfare and condition of services etc. Education is power and light through which any nation can see and attain growth and development. Pupils in most part of Katsina remain at home for a long time as a result of frequent insurgent attacks on some part of the state which can affect the attainment of quality primary education in the area and consequently contradict the constitutional provision of article No. 3 of the 1989 and 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria which states that "Education is the birth right of Nigerian citizen"

The problem of this study therefore hinged on the assessment of the extent to which insurgency has impacted on pupils enrollment and attainment of quality primary education in Katsina State Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The general objective of this research work is to investigate the impact of insurgency on Pupils enrolment and attainment of quality primary education in Katsina State, Nigeria. However, the research has the following specific objectives:

1. To find out stakeholders' perception on influence of insurgencies on primary school pupils' enrolment in Katsina state, Nigeria.
2. To access stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on gender in primary school pupils in Katsina state, Nigeria.
3. To determine stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' transition to the next level in Katsina state, Nigeria.
4. To ascertain the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' attendance to school in Katsina state, Nigeria.
5. To find out the stakeholders' perception on influence of insurgencies on primary school shutdown in Katsina state, Nigeria.
6. To evaluate the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' academic achievement in Katsina state, Nigeria.
7. To investigate the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' completion rate in Katsina state, Nigeria.
8. To determine the stakeholders' perception on influence of insurgencies on primary school completion rate in respect of gender in selected educational zone in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

In line with the objectives of the study, the following research questions will guide the research work:

1. What is the stakeholders' perception on influence of insurgencies on primary school pupils' enrolment in Katsina state, Nigeria?
2. What is the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on gender in primary school pupils in Katsina state, Nigeria?
3. What is the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' transition to the next level in Katsina state, Nigeria?
4. What is the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' attendance to school in Katsina state, Nigeria?
5. What is the stakeholders' perception on influence of insurgencies on primary school shutdown in Katsina state, Nigeria?
6. What is the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' academic achievement in Katsina state, Nigeria?
7. What is the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' completion rate in Katsina state, Nigeria?
8. What is the stakeholders' perception on influence of insurgencies on primary school completion rate with respect to gender in selected educational zone in Katsina state, Nigeria?

Significance of the study

This research work will be of significant importance to other researchers carrying out similar study either in the area or other part of the country and the world at large as a referral material. It will be equally significant to the government in providing quality education to the people in the area under study and Nigeria in general if the recommendations put forward by the researchers is put into consideration and implemented. The study will be of paramount importance to pupils and their parents if the recommendations suggested by the researchers are implemented by government in providing an enabling environment for teaching and learning for attainment of quality education by pupils in the state. Similarly, the study will be of importance to security personnel if the government adhered strictly to the recommendations put forward in their findings is given top priority.

Literature review

In this section, the researchers reviewed work related to the current study.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This section shall discuss both theories and concept:

Theoretical Overview

A theory is a contemplative and rational type of abstract or generalizing thinking or the result of such thinking. It also acts as a precursor to understanding of unexplained phenomenon or occurrences and gives a summary to a body of knowledge. It is also a set of interrelated principles designed to answer a question or explain a particular phenomenon. It provides us with different perspective with which to view our social world (Haruna, 2023). An explanation, idea or opinion based on thought observation and reasoning which has been tested and confirmed as general principle explaining a large number of related facts is also referred to as theory. The study is anchored on both conflict and structural functionalism theory.

Conflict Theory

Conflict theory was propounded by a German philosopher known as Karl Marx (1818-1883). He contends that there couldn't be development in any society without conflict as it emphasizes interest rather than norms and values in conflict. The pursuit of interest generates various types of conflict. Conflict is seen as a normal aspect of social life rather than an abnormal occurrence due to competition over resources is often the causes of conflict. Conflict theory views society as composed of different groups and interest competing for power and resources. Karl Marx

maintained that struggle among classes of people occurs in the history of modern societies where goods and materials are increasingly dominated by upper class (Bourgeoisies) while the lower class (proletariat) are left with little benefits. Karl Marx believes that as time goes on, one day the proletariat will organize and revolt against the existing system and classless society would emerge. The theory also explains that the group in power oppresses and exploits those that are not in power.

The researchers view on the theory of German revolutionary is of the opinion that those in position of power or governance continues to exploit and oppress the lower class without given them the desired attention one day revolution could take place where everybody can be equal leading to a classless society. The interpretation and relevance of this theory on the current study is that, if people in position continue with their corrupt practices without given the desired attention and quality education to the young children, one day they may grow into adult and revolt against them (bourgeoisies) and topple their power as nothing is forever because to everything that has beginning there must be an end to it. The insurgent groups are pressed to wall as a result of injustice from the government and decide to opt for violence to express their worry for government attention. This action is a justification of a statement made by late Aminu Kano and Obafemi Awolowo taggedged "The class warfare" as if a man who saw tomorrow, who said and I quote that " the "Nigeria will know no peace until the son of a nobody can become somebody without knowing anybody" (Mallam Aminu Kano) and Chief Obafemi Awolowo warned our leaders many years ago that " The children of the poor you failed to train will never let your children have peace " unless the desired attention is given. Above statement was corroborated by Sijibomi who also asserts that "If your neighbor is hungry, your chicken is not safe". He expresses further that, the events of the past years have shown that there is a wide and wild gap between the classes of youths in the nation. The Guardian Newspaper titled ObafemiAwolowo: The class warfare and the man who saw tomorrow, (Gbenga, 2020).

The rationale for the adoption of conflict theory is that; if the young learners are trained in the proper channel and acquire the right type of attitude and values, one day they will grow up as adults and revolt against the corrupt leaders and resist the oppressive treatment meted on them by taking over the mantle of leadership in order to bring about sanity in the society and consequently leading to attainment of quality education and the desired objectives of primary education in Katsina State.

Structural Functionalism Theory:

Structural functionalism theory is a sociological theory that attempts to explain why society functions the way it does by focusing on the relationships between the various social institutions that made up the society. Herbert Spencer (1820 – 1903) an English philosopher and Biologist saw similarities between society and the human body. He argued that as various organs of human body work to keep the body functioning, so also the various parts of the society work together to keep the society functioning effectively. The parts of the society referred to were the social institutions or pattern of beliefs and behaviors focused on social needs, like the government, law, media, economy, family, healthcare, education, and religion. But this study focuses on the government, law and education. Durkheim believed that the society is a complex system of interrelated and interdependent that work together to maintain stability. The theory states that society work together to maintain the life of society and that of an individual like human body. The theory maintains that if there is disorder, the society may become disorganized and experience change. In an agreement with the view of theory; the researcher is of the view that both the society and educational systems are interconnected and interdependent to each other and so therefore, once one aspect or level is affected it will affect others. For instance, if primary education which is the focus of this study is affected it will affect the quality and attainment of the rest level of education from achieving its objectives and quality.

Methodology

The study area comprises of thirty four (34) Local Government Areas (LGA) with four (4) education Zones which are Katsina, Daura, Dutsinma and Funtua Zones respectively. The current study dwell on Dutsinma and Katsina educational zone only.

A four points Likert scale were used to measure the stakeholders' perception on influence of insurgencies on primary school pupils. The strongly agree (SA) = 4, agree (A) = 3, disagree (D) = 2, strongly disagree (SD) = 1). The linear scale indicates the level at which respondents agree or disagree with each statement. A mean score of 2.5 and above indicates that the respondents show a high level of agreement to a particular statement and whereas, a mean less than 2.5 indicates the respondents show a high extent of disagreement to a particular statement as represented'.

Research Design

The researchers use descriptive survey research method for the study. This method was used because it can be used to designate any research activity in which the investigators gather data from a large population for the purpose of examining the characteristics, opinion or intensions of that population (Emaikwu 2008). A descriptive survey design is selected because of its high degree of representativeness and the ease with which a researcher could obtain views of the respondents or participants opinion. The rational or justification for using survey research design is that, it deals mainly with the opinion of large group of people and it gives more opportunity to sample wide range of population. Survey research design is also suitable as it can be used to gather data for a large number of subjects which is widely used in the study of significant educational problem and has profound influence in the field of education as much as in any other social science discipline (Emaikwu, 2008).

Population of the Study: The target population of the study comprises of all the teachers and head teachers of primary schools in Katsina and Dutsin-ma educational zones as well as some officials of the ministry of education, Katsina State.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique: The study use simple random sampling technique to obtain data from the respondents in the study area, and purposive sampling procedure was used for selection of the sample size. A sample size of 381 respondents was selected from the total number of respondents' spread across the study area at 95% confidence level and 5% level of precision as determined by Research Advisors (2006) table of specification for sample selection.

Method of Data Collection: The researchers develop structured questionnaires for primary schools teachers and head teachers. The questionnaires was administered with the help of research assistants and collected back on an appointed date agreed by the researchers and the respondents to avoid cases of omission and retrieval of the questionnaires distributed. Information was also collected through secondary data which are records of documents from relevant offices such as UBE offices, NUT offices, Ministry of Education in the State LGEA offices respectively.

Method of Data Analysis: The data collected was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistic like simple percentage, mean and standard deviation was used to answer research questions posed by the study.

Results presentation and discussions of finding

The results of this study were presented in tables based on eight (8) research questions, as follows;

Research Question One: What is the stakeholders' perception on influence of insurgencies on primary school pupils' enrolment in Katsina state, Nigeria?

The stakeholders' perception was measured by looking at the mean score. Statements having mean score above 2.5 is either agreed (A= 3) or strongly agreed (SA= 4) considered as having agreed with the statements while mean score below 2.5 is either disagreed (D= 2) or strongly disagreed (DA= 1) indicated stakeholders' disagreement with the statements.

Table 1: Decrease in pupils' enrolment due to insurgencies

Educational zones	Items	4	3	2	1	Means
Katsina	Pupils' enrolment in primary schools remarkably declines in areas prone to insurgencies Katsina state	648	9	0	0	3.98
	Challenges of insurgencies compels families within the catchment areas flee their homes and this negatively affect pupils; enrolment in school	600	45	0	0	3.91
	Incessant attacks of insurgencies on communities made parents to be afraid of enrolling their children in school	564	72	0	0	3.85
	Many parents in such unsecured areas have lost interest in education and such affect pupils' enrolment	588	54	0	0	3.89
Total		600.00	45.00	0.00	0.00	3.91
Dutsinma	Pupils' enrolment in primary schools remarkably declines in areas prone to insurgency Katsina state	732	0	0	0	4.44
	Challenges of insurgency compels families within the catchment areas flee their homes and this negatively affect pupils; enrolment in school	648	63	0	0	4.31
	Incessant attacks of insurgency on communities made parents to be afraid of enrolling their children in school	672	45	0	0	4.35
	Many parents in such unsecured areas have lost interest in education and such affect pupils' enrolment	720	9	0	0	4.42
Total		693.00	29.25	0.00	0.00	4.38

Table 1: This dealt with the perception of stakeholders on influence of insurgencies on primary school pupils' enrolment was measured by looking at the mean score. All the stakeholders' perception in both Katsina and Dutsinma recorded mean score above (≥ 3.85) indicating high level of agreement with the statements. However, highest scores were recorded in Dutsinma with (≥ 4.31) mean scores. This could be ascribed to the cases of banditry around Dutsinma which is relatively higher than what being reported in Katsina. The result of the finding is in line with study carried out by Mohammed and Olowoselu (2015) where they noted that frequent abduction of school girls in their dormitory, occasional kidnapping of school girls on their way to school in Damaturu have reduced their attendance in schools drastically.

Research Question two: What is the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on gender in primary school pupils in Katsina state, Nigeria?

Table 2: Insurgencies greatly affect female pupils than male pupils

Educational zones	Items	4	3	2	1	Means
Katsina	Insurgencies attack greatly affects female pupils' enrolment more than males in schools.	564	72	0	0	3.85
	As a result to insurgencies attack, many pupils particularly, females have been withdrawn from schools thus affecting their enrolment and academic achievement.	588	54	0	0	3.89
Total		576.00	63.00	0.00	0.00	3.87
Dutsinma	Insurgencies attack greatly affects female pupils' enrolment more than males in schools.	564	126	0	0	4.18
	As a result to insurgencies attack, many pupils particularly, females have been withdrawn from schools thus affecting their enrolment and academic achievement.	624	81	0	0	4.27
Total		594.00	103.50	0.00	0.00	4.23

Table 2: For the effect of insurgencies with respect to gender. The two educational zones of Katsina and Dutsinma showed female pupils to be comparatively affected by insurgencies related issues than male pupils. The stakeholders' perception strongly agreed with the statement (≥ 3.85) mean score. Above analysis is in agreement with the research work carried out by Mohammed and Olowoselu (2015) who noted that most educational activities on girls education in mostly affected states has been suspended since most teachers and school heads in region are among the internally displaced persons.

Research Question three: What is the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' transition to the next level in Katsina state, Nigeria?

Table 3: Insurgencies affect pupils' transition to the next level

Educational zones	Items	4	3	2	1	Means
Katsina	Insurgencies attack affect pupils transition to the next level of education in my locality	576	63	0	0	3.87
Dutsinma		648	63	0	0	4.31
Total		612.00	63.00	0.00	0.00	4.09

Table 3: On the effect of insurgencies on pupils' transition to the next level, the stakeholders' perception across the two educational zones strongly agreed with the statement which represent (≥ 3.87) mean score. Most educational activities in the affected educational zones has been suspended since pupils and most teachers and school heads in area are displaced due to insurgency attack. These will definitely affect children's transition to the next level. Above findings is in line with the report in Leadership newspaper which reveals that about 19 public schools were shut down in Katsina State in the year 2022 due to insurgency attacks. Once school is shut down, it will affect the learners' progress and achievement.

Research Question four: What is the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' attendance to school in Katsina state, Nigeria?

Table 4: Insurgencies affect pupils' attendance to school

Educational zones	Items	4	3	2	1	Means
Katsina	Insurgent attack on communities made parents to take their children away and thus affects school attendance	540	81	0	0	3.76
	Some families are separated as a result of insurgents attack, many pupils cannot connect with their parents and will prevent them from thinking of going back to school in my community	588	54	0	0	3.89
	Some pupils that were scattered as a result of insecurity may have difficulty in returning to school and definitely affect their attendance.	540	90	0	0	3.82
	Pupils who lost their parents as a result of insurgencies are out of school in my community and thereby reducing school population.	552	81	0	0	3.84
	The displacement of many families due to insurgents' attack has led to many pupils to drop out of school which adversely affect the achievement.	600	45	0	0	3.91
	Pupils who lost their parents as a result of insurgents attack are no longer attending school due to financial support and has affected their academic achievement tremendously.	576	63	0	0	3.87
Total		566.00	69.00	0.00	0.00	3.85
Dutsinma	Insurgent attack on communities made parents to take their children away and thus affects school attendance.	660	54	0	0	4.33
	Some families are separated as a result of insurgents attack, many pupils cannot connect with their parents and will prevent them from thinking of going back to school in my community.	636	72	0	0	4.29
	Some pupils that were scattered as a result of insecurity may have difficulty in returning to school and definitely affect their attendance.	624	81	0	0	4.27
	Pupils who lost their parents as a result of insurgencies are out of school in my community and thereby reducing school population.	600	99	0	0	4.24
	The displacement of many families due to insurgents attack has led to many pupils to drop out of school which adversely affect the achievement.	624	81	0	0	4.27
	Pupils who lost their parents as a result of insurgents attack are no longer attending school due to financial support and have affected their academic achievement tremendously.	672	45	0	0	4.35
Total		636.00	72.00	0.00	0.00	4.29

Table 4: The result revealed ≥ 3.76 mean score in both Katsina and Dutsinma educational zones. Thus, insurgencies affect primary school pupils' attendance to school in Katsina state. This study is

in line with the research findings by Umaru & Terhemba (2014), they noted that insecurity and terrorism affects schools attendance as school were shut down due to frequent attack of school by terrorist in Damaturu metropolises and children attendance was low. This finding was also corroborated by Leadership newspaper which reveals that about 19 public schools were shut down in Katsina State in the year 2022 due to insurgency attacks.

Research Question five: What is the stakeholders' perception on influence of insurgencies on primary school shutdown in Katsina state, Nigeria?

Table 5: Insurgencies cause school shutdown

Educational zones	Items	4	3	2	1	Means
Katsina	Schools are forced to shut following incessant attacks by insurgents in the communities.	552	81	0	0	3.84
Dutsinma		624	81	0	0	4.27
Total		588.00	81.00	0.00	0.00	4.05

Table 5: The stakeholders' perception in all the educational zones showed insurgencies influenced primary school shutdown in Katsina state, represented by ≥ 3.84 mean score. Umaru & Terhemba (2014) in their study noted that insecurity and terrorism affects schools attendance as school were shut down due to frequent attack of school by terrorist in Damaturu metropolises. This event was equally confirmed by Godwin in Leadership newspaper which indicates that about 19 public schools were shut down in Katsina State in the year 2022 due to terrorist attacks.

Research Question six: What is the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' academic achievement in Katsina state, Nigeria?

Table 6: Insurgencies affect pupils' academic achievement

Educational zones	Items	4	3	2	1	Means
Katsina	Insurgents' attack made many teachers stayed away from schools and this as well made pupils attendant at schools very difficult which will affect their achievement.	624	27	0	0	3.95
	Insurgents' attack disrupts school working hours; thus this affects pupils' academic achievement due to divided attention of staff and the pupils.	648	9	0	0	3.98
	As insecurity expels many families out of their homes as such it is very difficult for the students to stay on at schools for learning.	552	81	0	0	3.84
	Most of the parents who lost their means of livelihood due to insurgencies may not be able to further train their children and this will affect their academic achievement.	444	162	0	0	3.67
Total		567.00	69.75	0.00	0.00	3.86
Dutsinma	Insurgents attack made many teachers stayed away from schools and this as well made pupils attendant at schools very difficult which will affect their achievement.	708	18	0	0	4.40
	Insurgents' attack disrupts school	684	36	0	0	4.36

	working hours; thus this affects pupils' academic achievement due to divided attention of staff and the pupils.					
	As insecurity expels many families out of their homes as such it is very difficult for the students to stay on at schools for learning.	660	54	0	0	4.33
	Most of the parents who lost their means of livelihood due to insurgencies may not be able to further train their children and this will affect their academic achievement.	444	216	0	0	4.00
Total		624.00	81.00	0.00	0.00	4.27

Table 6: The result recorded ≥ 3.86 mean score. Thus, the stakeholders' percept that insurgencies negatively affect primary school pupils' academic achievement in the state. The result of the study carried out by Olawuwo, Atiku, & Hussaini (2023) equally support the result of the recent study as their own findings also revealed that 66.8% of the respondents were of the opinion that insecurity causes closure of schools; 63.6% opined that insecurity makes teachers to abandon teaching; 69.5% agreed that insecurity causes pupils poor quality educational achievement on the area.

Research Question seven: What is the stakeholders' perception on effect of insurgencies on primary school pupils' completion rate in Katsina state, Nigeria?

Table 7: insurgencies hinders school completion rate for all pupils

Educational zones	Items	4	3	2	1	Means
Katsina	Some pupils may not be able to complete their primary education due to insurgencies threats leading to inability to achieve the desired quality education.	624	27	0	0	3.95
Dutsinma		684	36	0	0	4.36
Total		654.00	31.50	0.00	0.00	4.15

Table 7: The stakeholders' perception represented by ≥ 4.15 mean score indicated that insurgencies negatively affect completion rate of primary school pupils in Katsina state. Above analysis is in alliance with the research work carried out by Isah, Tukur, & Auwal (2023). They reported that children attendant in school was very low and most of them drop out of school due to banditry attacks which affects their attainment of quality education. The result of the study carried out by Olawuwo, Atiku, & Hussaini (2023) equally revealed that 66.8% of the respondents were of the opinion that insecurity causes closure of schools; 63.6% opined that insecurity makes teachers to abandon teaching; 69.5% agreed that insecurity causes poor quality of educational achievement.

Research Question eight: What is the stakeholders' perception on influence of insurgencies on primary school completion rate with respect to gender in selected educational zone in Katsina state, Nigeria?

Table 8: Insurgencies may hinder school completion rate and female pupils are affected than male pupils

Educational zones	Items	4	3	2	1	Means
Katsina	School completion rate especially for female students may be affected as a result of insurgencies in my community.	648	9	0	0	3.98
Dutsinma		696	27	6	0	4.42
Total		672.00	18.00	3.00	0.00	4.20

Table 8: The mean score showed ≥ 4.20 about the stakeholders' perception that insurgencies is most likely to have higher on female pupils' completion rate in Katsina state is in agreement with the research work carried out by Abiodun, Opatoki, Adeyemo, & Obi (2020) where they reported that many schools in the northern border areas of Borno State were closed down between 2012 and 2013 because of Boko Haram attacks or the pervasive fear of violence. They further explain that a teacher at Mobbar Central Primary School, in Damasak Local Government, painted a dismal picture of the situation in the northern part of the state. No schools have operated in 20 out of 27 local government authorities that make up Borno State since March 2014 as at the time of the conduct of their study.

Conclusion

This research work x-rayed stakeholders' perception on impact of insurgencies on pupils' enrolment and achievement of quality primary education in Katsina State, Nigeria. Eight objectives and eight research questions were used to guide the study and each question was digested into four items statement to ease understanding of the questions for the respondents. The descriptive statistics used for the analysis of the data. Addressing the issue of insurgencies attacks on schools requires a multi-faceted approach that involves the collaboration of various stakeholders, including the government, law enforcement agencies, school authorities, communities, and international organizations. Implementing the recommendations will make it possible to mitigate against the impact of insurgency attacks on pupils attendance and create a safer learning environment for learners and staff for adequate pupils' enrollment and quality education to thrive. It is essential to prioritize the safety and education of children and provide them with the necessary support to continue their studies even in challenging circumstances.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the research work, the following recommendations were made for pupils' enrolment and achieving quality education in Katsina State.

1. The government should provide employment opportunity and also empower young graduates with skill acquisition inform of entrepreneurship and loan to be self-employed to cope with current realities of unemployment and keep them busy as an idle mind they said is a devil workshop.
2. There should be expansion of entrepreneurship skills education in our educational system by incorporating entrepreneurship education in the curriculum at all levels of our educational system from primary to tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Acquiring entrepreneurship skills education after graduation will enable young graduate to be self-employed without waiting for white collar job or join bad wagon of terrorists.
3. Improved security measures should be provided around school environment to deter insurgency attacks. Such measures includes installing surveillance cameras, posting of enough security personnel to support local security guards, and setting up security checkpoints can help create concussive environment for pupils and teachers.
4. Adequate funding should be allocated to education sector as recommended by UNESCO at both national and state level to cater for teachers' training and welfare to enable them put in their best by giving the pupils desired quality education.

5. Community engagement and cooperation with law enforcement agencies is necessary to address the issue of insurgency attacks. Collaboration of the local security and village heads and leaders can help in gathering valuable information to prevent attacks.
6. Security agencies should take reasonable steps in line with Nigeria's responsibility under international human rights law to protect pupils, teachers, schools, and all those in Nigeria's territory from insurgencies.
7. Remote Learning options is advisable for remote villages. In areas where the risk of insurgency attacks is high, remote learning options should be considered. Online classes or distance learning programs can ensure continuous access to education without exposing children's and staff to physical threats of insurgency.
8. The Federal and state government should ensure that adequate security personnel are posted to communities prone to insurgencies. The personnel's welfare in terms of motivation as well as adequate security gadgets be properly taken care of for smooth and effective running of academic activities in such areas.
9. The national assembly should enact law to empower for security agents to arrest, investigate, prosecute and give severe punishment inform of live imprisonment death sentence to terrorists responsible for abduction and attacks on school pupils and teachers as deterrence to others.

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